

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ON BUSINESS AND THE BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: The article examines how digital economy technologies are changing people's living conditions and economic behavior. The focus is on business behavior and new business environment opportunities. In particular, changes in business strategy, competition, new marketing and customer service opportunities, the emergence of new sources of profit and competitiveness factors are being analyzed. Organizational forms and new methods of doing business in the conditions of digital transformation and digital economy are analyzed..

Keywords: digital economy, digital transformation, artificial intelligence, customer experience, collaborative innovation, price discrimination, platform method, competitive disruption, digital capital, creative capital.

1. Introduction

The technological basis of the digital economy is being created on the basis of the discoveries of the Fourth industrial Revolution. Among them are artificial intelligence, distributed data, the Internet of things and for things, blockchain, mining centers, big data and cloud storage, digital platforms, 3D and then 4D printing. The technological design of various systems is used to solve specific tasks.

The digital economy, growing on the basis of the information economy, can be defined as its continuation in a new quality after an unprecedented and disruptive technological breakthrough as a result of the Fourth industrial Revolution [8, p. 52], which is characterized by a nonlinear (exponential) speed of innovation, the depth and scale of penetration of digital technologies, the power of

influence of digital complexes and systems [13]. Their application changes a lot in the way of thinking and motivation of decisions, i.e. not only in productivity, but also in economic behavior, in the principles of organization and operation of companies and the entire economic mechanism. Technological achievements of the Fourth industrial Revolution had a serious impact on the business environment and its participants, who completely switched to the use of digital technologies, combining industrial technologies with digital ones. What is it? "Digitalization" has had an impact: □ firstly, on the ways of organizing and conducting business, its marketing strategies; □ secondly, on providing business with resources; третьих thirdly, on production and transaction costs (organizational, managerial, communication, costs of receiving, processing and storing information), which in the digital sphere are sharply reduced or disappear altogether □ четвер fourth, on the network effect and the scale effect, which are becoming global. Customer relationship strategies. The use of digital technologies, including artificial intelligence, and the intensification of competition give rise to trends such as deepening relations with the buyer, communicating with him in the digital environment and responsive to changes in his preferences. The client's problems, their solution, become a source of profit. In the digital economy, work with the buyer is individualized, involvement in his tasks and empathy are practiced. The value of customer experience is growing, which also becomes a source of profit and at the same time an acquired good in the segment of inter-company relations (B2B). On the basis of individualization of demand satisfaction and deepening of relations with the buyer, the probability of price discrimination increases, which is also, on the one hand, an additional source of profit, and on the other, an additional opportunity for the buyer. Digital technologies, saving transaction costs, and

sometimes reducing them to zero, generating new potential, and at the same time new requests and requirements for the market, accelerate business and production. As a result, the life of not only the product, but also the company is shortened. So, in the Standard&Poor 500 rating, the life span of large corporations has been reduced from 60 years to 18. Business culture, company culture is changing towards the need for leadership and self-perception in the structure of their organization (individual mental embeddedness in the company). Organizational and leadership ability to learn and fundamental changes is needed, the speed of which will only increase. This implies the need for an innovative culture of the company, the ability to create and implement effective projects at high speed. All this leaves no room for routine, administrative costs and stereotypes, the so-called silo of the company. Competition is moving from the sphere of cost reduction to the sphere of creativity. Opportunities are expanding and project financing is accelerating, for example, through the collection of tokens for a creative and well-designed project with transparent efficiency and profitability through the blockchain system [2]. Disruptivity has a multidirectional impact on business. Many industries are introducing technologies that create completely new ways to meet the needs of the buyer and undermine the old value chains. For example, new technologies of energy storage and networks accelerate the shift in the energy industry towards the decentralization of sources and distribution of energy. 3D and 4D printing technologies accelerate and optimize the availability of components that repair and assembly companies can make individually. At the same time, the organization is exempt from the costs of search, delivery, storage and non-compliance with the required standard or individual characteristics.

Real-time information and unique customer knowledge ensure high asset performance, which contributes to further technological development. New conditions in working with customers. Breakthrough results in science and economics are provided by the widespread use of artificial intelligence: from software for the discovery of new medicines to algorithms that identify our cultural interests and predict our behavior. Many similar schemes are built on the basis of information traces that buyers leave in the digital field, for example, while on social networks, browsing company websites or other information. In particular, applications such as, for example, Siri (from Apple) to a powerful artificial intelligence subsystem (AI Field) are already being used [11, p. 22]. By processing individual information about the users of the sites, they perform the role of intellectual consultants, forming the "surrounding mind". It is an intelligent digital interactive environment that surrounds the user with automated personal consultants. Electronic devices study and predict needs, help to make a choice and realize it, forming a person's personal ecosystem. By the way, this solves the problem that arose after the third industrial revolution, which consumers faced in the information economy – the difficulty of selecting meaningful information with its abundance [9]. So, being in the digital environment of both the business and the buyer, using artificial intelligence to search and process information helps the business to conduct in-depth work with the client, individualizing marketing. Automatically processed targeted advertising information, personalized through artificial intelligence, in the digital field acts as an offer to a specific buyer, taking into account his individual preferences and capabilities. The information can be improved until the offer becomes interesting to the client and gets to the point. Individualized market segments can be created on the basis of automated

information processing. Moreover, the seller pays an incomparably low price for this compared to traditional methods. The larger the number of buyers, the smaller its unit (average) transaction and digital costs. Thus, the terms of sale of many goods on the web are approaching perfect price discrimination. Similarly, the possibilities of multi-market price discrimination are expanding. Here, the increased individualism of the user in the digital environment, an in-depth approach to solving his problems, becomes a reliable protection against the buyer's transition to other market segments. At the same time, the principle of justice and social efficiency is not violated [7, p. 62]. Changes in competition. During the transition to the digital economy, there are changes in the conditions of competition. For example, competitors can become partners by combining on the basis of digital platforms and sharing. At the same time, the opposite phenomenon appears – competitive undermining. This is an unexpected appearance of competitive advantages for a beginner, for example, due to a startup or access to global digital platforms for research, development, marketing, fast sales and distribution. Such companies overtake reputable old-timers in terms of speed, cost and quality of delivery of goods or services. Another source of competitive disruption that digital technologies provide is the ability to cross industry boundaries. This makes it possible to use customer bases, infrastructure and technologies at the intersectoral level. You can imagine how the company's efficiency increases, how costs are sharply reduced. An example is the introduction of telecommunications companies in the automotive and healthcare industries. The size of the company can also become a competitive advantage, provided efficiency. All these are shifts on the supply side. Disrupting competitors in business can also be influenced by changes in market demand. Digital technologies create

transparency, new models of consumer behavior based on access to mobile networks and data. In response, companies adapt the methods of development, marketing and delivery, are forced to create new products and services.

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